

Role of biomarkers in the forensic investigation of arson mainly bride burning cases – in India[†]

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Abstract : Arson is a widely prevalent crime done for multiple reasons. Homicidal bride burning, a typical example of arson, particularly prevalent in India, Bangladesh and other South Asian countries for monetary reasons and on other pretexts.

The exhibits for bride burning cases from different parts of West Bengal and Delhi were received by the Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata for investigation. Gas chromatograph-Mass spectrometric measurements of the analyzates particularly fuels (kerosene) extracted from fire debris residues showed the presence of high boiling hydrocarbon fractions and particularly biomarkers in all exhibits in spite of the absence of low boiling fractions in some cases. The biomarkers were common as well as variable depending on the source of fuel. But the presence of biomarkers was the undisputable proof for the use of fire accelerators like kerosene in the burning cases.

Keywords : Forensic science, arson, biomarkers, bride burning, gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer, kerosene.

Introduction

Arson is an extremely offending crime of intentionally setting properties or other belongings to fire. However, arson is quite broad based and varied in nature depending on the intention of arson. Connor¹ have identified and elaborated different reasons for arson in United States of America which are presented as what follows.

Arson for profit like

(i) Insurance fraud.

(ii) Welfare fraud.

(iii) Business related frauds. This is divided into sub heads :

(a) Eliminating competition.

(b) Organized crime like arson for hire business, bankruptcy, scam, demolition and rehabilitation scheme, building strippers.

Motivations for arson are

(i) Revenge, spite and jealousy.

(ii) Vanity.

(iii) Juvenile fire setters.

(iv) Crime concealment.

(v) Psychological compulsions like mania and depression, pyromania, schizophrenia.

(vi) Mass civil disobedience (riot).

(vii) Terrorism.

Arson is one of the major crimes in USA¹ though arson has been reported to be contained to some extent. But arson is prevalent to a limited extent in other countries (depending on economic condition and existing laws) as the human psychologies have some common universal features.

However, in India and in other third world countries, arson like setting fire to thatched huts, buildings etc. due to animosity, political or gang rivalries or to evict tenants or occupants from their positions for financial gains or mass riots is also menacingly high. Blasting of improvised explosive devices a typical case of arson is also of

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frequent occurrence. But the calculated cases of homicidal burning of bride mainly for non fulfillment of monetary demands like dowry, are the most heinous offences of arson. Other homicidal burning cases may be included.

The main points of investigation for arson are

(i) Circumstantial evidences like the burn patterns, the condition of the articles, and physical damage of the fire scene.

(ii) Suspected illicit love affairs of the bride or family trouble by in laws.

(iii) Husband's illicit involvement and other factors mainly monetary.

(iv) Fire dynamics.

(v) Rate of heat release and flame spread.

(vi) Quantum of product loss and other damages.

(vii) Ignition sources and ignition thresholds of fuel (kerosene, diesel, gasoline, paint thinner etc.) used.

(viii) Cause of fire like electric short circuits, faulty electrical appliances, burning cigarette butts and light match sticks etc.

But the drawback is lack of comprehensive body of data which necessarily imply acquittal of culprits²⁻⁴. Most arson cases mentioned above require fire investigators or fire service personnel and the law enforcing officials and these cases do not usually fall under the purview of forensic investigation. However, improvised explosive device blast and bride burning cases fall under the purview of forensic investigation.

Only e homicidal bride burning cases are the subject matter of the present investigation. Arson or homicidal bride burning is prevalent in India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal, Malaysia etc.⁵. Collections of the physical evidences of fire, the origin of fire and charred materials are some of the primary tasks of the police.

The bride burning are deliberate and cold blooded operations perpetrated by the criminals according to their convenience by taking enough precautions to misguide the investigators. Destruction of evidences is done by methods like water flushing, throwing mud and sands or by use of fire extinguishers. The removal of major indicators of arson is usually done before the investigation team reaches the site. Others are only a chain of circumstantial evidences which should be utilized for investiga-

tion and ultimate correlation with scientific evidences to ascertain the reasons of arson and comprehend the culprits, if possible. The investigators have to establish motive, modus operandi and the suspect^{5,6}. The investigations of potential arson cases demand immediate attention; otherwise the physical evidences establishing corpus delicti of arson will rapidly dissipate. Evaporation of traces of most of the accelerators of fire i.e. petroleum products like kerosene, diesel, gasoline etc. are expected if the investigating team reaches the site after a considerable time^{6,7}.

Exhibits for arson (suspected bride burnings cases) are usually sent from different parts of West Bengal, Delhi and adjoining areas to Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata, for analytical investigations and report the findings before the judiciary.

The results of the investigative analysis of exhibits of suspected bride burning cases are reported in this communication.

Experimental

The experimental samples were the exhibits for bride burning cases from different parts of West Bengal, Delhi and adjoining areas.

In bride burning cases, preliminary first hand investigation and information were collected from the law enforcing authorities. Usually burnt clothes, burnt bed sheets, burnt rags and rugs were sent as exhibits. Some of the exhibits had the smell of kerosene but absent in most of the cases. Fire debris residues and control samples, well separated from burnt exhibits were collected from the scene of burning.

Solvents like acetone, ether and other chemicals used were of AnalaR quality from E. Merck (India). Burnt portions of the exhibits or ashes collected from the scene (fire debris) were dissolved in acetone or in ether solutions and the filtered solutions were subjected to Thin Layer Chromatography and finally to Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry analysis. Similarly, unaffected portions i.e. sufficiently away from the burnt portions of the exhibits were used as controls. The controls were treated in the same way as done in case of exhibits. Kerosene samples were collected from different localities of Kolkata, but no sample of kerosene from Delhi or adjoining areas could be collected.

Instruments :*Gas chromatograph-Mass spectrometer :*

The identification and characterization of the explosives and hydrocarbons present as petroleum base materials of the burnt exhibits and control samples were made using Perkin-Elmer Claurus 500 model GC-MS by injecting variable volumes of the experimental solutions in ether through Elite 5 MS column (30 m). Oven temperature was programmed between 70 °C (1 min) and 280 °C/300 °C (5 min/10 min) with 10 °C/min increment generally. The injector and interface temperatures were 150 °C/180 °C and 200 °C. The system was run at constant flow mode, the rate of carrier gas (helium) flow being 1 ml/min. MS parameters for the analysis of explosives were : EI⁺ mode, source temperature 150°, energy 70 eV, mass range scanned 30–400 atomic mass unit.

Results

In bride burning cases, preliminary first hand investigation and information were collected from the law enforcing authorities. The bodies were sent for medical examinations or post mortem studies. No viscera and body fluids or portions of charred body were sent to the Forensic Science Laboratory. The main drawbacks for most of the bride burning cases were

(i) Lack of proper precautions to protect the volatile components present in the exhibits.

(ii) Considerable time lag in between the dates of accident, collection of samples and the analytical examination of exhibits. In bride burning or other burning cases, kerosene was invariably the fire accelerator used. Ten kerosene samples available at different markets of Kolkata at different times were processed and dissolved in ether and were subjected to GC-MS analysis. Nine most abundant peaks shown in Table 1 were obtained in all cases. Besides these peaks, other prominent compounds like chemical markers (Table 2) and important biomarkers (Table 3) were obtained though these were present in minute quantities. However, chemical markers and biomarkers were found to be slightly different from each other depending on the origin of kerosene. Some higher hydrocarbons were also detected but their concentrations were sufficiently low. Analysis of kerosene samples from Delhi and adjoining areas could not be performed but nature of hydrocarbons should be similar with possible variations of chemical markers and biomarkers.

Table 1. The most dominating hydrocarbons found in all market available kerosene

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	4.5	Decane	C ₁₀ H ₂₂	142
2.	5.9	Undecane	C ₁₁ H ₂₄	156
3.	7.34	Dodecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	170
4.	8.75	Tridecane	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184
5.	10.10	Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198
6.	11.38	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
7.	12.61	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
8.	13.77	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
9.	14.88	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268

Table 2. Chemical markers and other compounds found in market available kerosene

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	4.80	<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene	C ₆ H ₄ Cl ₂	146
2.	5.59	4-Cresol	C ₇ H ₈ O	108
3.	5.76	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	124
4.	7.27	Naphthalene	C ₁₀ H ₈	128
5.	8.34	Unsaturated decane	C ₁₀ H ₂₀	140
6.	10.48	Naphthalene-2,6-dimethyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
7.	10.54	Naphthalene-1,6-dimethyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
8.	11.48	Butylated hydroxy toluene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220
9.	22.19	Octacosane	C ₂₈ H ₅₈	394
10.	23.05	Nonacosane	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	408
11.	25.27	Tetracontane	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	562

Table 3. Biomarkers found in different market available kerosene

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	21.14	Norolean-12-ene	C ₂₉ H ₄₈	396
2.	22.22	3-Keto-urs-12-ene	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O	424
3.	22.53	14B-Pregnane	C ₂₁ H ₃₆	288
4.	23.05	Urs-12-en-28-ol	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426
5.	24.00	Alpha amyirin	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426
6.	24.99	Friedelan-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426
	24.02	Cholest-5-en-3-ol	C ₂₇ H ₄₆ O	386
6.	24.32	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410
	26.03	Cholesta-3,5-dien-7-one	C ₂₇ H ₄₂ O	382
8.	26.39	Cholesta-4,6-dien-3-ol	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O	384

The results of GC-MS analysis of fuels (extracted with ether) of exhibits from the different parts of West Bengal, Delhi and adjoining areas are presented in Tables 4 to 15 without the common peaks (sometimes they were lost in

Table 4. Compounds and biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 1 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	9.73	Dodecane-2,6,10-trimethyl	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
2.	9.91	Biphenyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₀	154
3.	10.06	Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198
4.	10.45	2,3-Dimethyl naphthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
5.	10.52	1,6-Dimethyl naphthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	156
6.	10.84	Pristane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
7.	10.89	Tetracosane	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	338
8.	24.99	Friedelane-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426

Table 5. Compounds and biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 2 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	10.06	Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198
2.	11.35	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
3.	11.44	Butylated hydroxy toluene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220
4.	12.57	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
5.	13.73	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
6.	24.99	Friedelane-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426

Table 6. Biomarker found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 3 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compound	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	24.87	Friedelane-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426

Table 7. Biomarker found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 4 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compound	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	24.94	Friedelane-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426

Table 8. Biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 5 (Delhi Area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	24.17	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410
2.	24.93	Cholesta-4,6-dien-3-ol (3-beta)	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O	384

Table 9. Biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 6 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compound	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	23.52	Cholest-4-en-3-one	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O	384
2.	24.26	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O	424
3.	24.51	5-Alpha, 8-Alpha, 14-Beta cholestane	C ₂₇ H ₄₈	372

Table 10. Compounds and biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 7 (South Bengal area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	8.63	Hydroquinone	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂	110
2.	11.37	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
3.	12.59	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
4.	13.78	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
5.	14.08	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
6.	20.92	14B-Pregnane	C ₂₁ H ₃₆	288
7.	22.03	Hop-22(29)-en-3-beta-ol	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	426

Table 11. Compounds and biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 8 (South Bengal area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	11.36	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
2.	12.57	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
3.	13.76	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
4.	14.05	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
5.	23.46	Nonacosane	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	408
6.	24.28	14B-Pregnane	C ₂₁ H ₃₆	288
7.	25.003	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	410

Table 12. Compounds and biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 9 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	11.03	Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	212
2.	12.24	Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226
3.	13.40	Octadecane	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254
4.	13.85	Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268
5.	23.68	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410
6.	24.63	(8R,12R,13R)-8,12-Epoxy-13-hydroxy-labd-14-ene	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O	299

Table 13. Biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 10 (North Bengal area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	12.37	2,3,5-Trimethylnaphthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₄	170
2.	13.31	Cadalin	C ₁₅ H ₂₈	198

Table 14. Biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 11 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	17.79	1-Octadecanol (stenol)	C ₁₈ H ₃₈ O	270
2.	24.53	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410

Table 15. Biomarkers found in burnt extracts - Exhibit 12 (Delhi area)

Sl. no.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Formula	Molecular weight
1.	19.53	Heptadecane-2,6,10,15-tetramethyl	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296
2.	23.92	Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410

the process of burning). Only special features are presented. Total ion chromatogram of the control kerosene samples and other exhibits are presented in Figs. 1 to 8. The mass spectrum of some biomarkers as obtained are presented in Figs. 9 to 14.

Discussion

Forensic analysis of accelerants in fire debris is of great interest and has been extensively studied by various workers⁶⁻¹⁷.

Prosecution of crime of arson is almost impossible in many cases. The reasons are

(i) Lack of physical evidence at the crime scene.

(ii) Difficulty in associating a particular suspect with any physical evidence like presence of ignitable liquid residue.

The detection and identification of an ignitable liquid residue (i.e. accelerants of fire) is the first step in the investigation of arson. Every suspected arson scene is unique as the variants are many and the variables can affect the extraction and identification of any ignitable liquid residue. Literature providing the method of extraction from the fire debris, the analysis of the extracts and their interpretations are available⁶⁻⁹.

The American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) Institution⁹ published manuals for the extraction of ignitable liquids and for the classification and interpretation of experimental analytical results. In many cases, ignitable, residues are very low in presence of bulk back-

Fig. 1. Total ion chromatogram of a market available kerosene.

Fig. 2. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 3).

Fig. 3. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 5).

Fig. 4. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 6).

Fig. 5. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 7).

Fig. 6. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 8).

Fig. 7. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 9).

Fig. 8. Total ion chromatogram of a burnt exhibit extracts (Exhibit 11).

Fig. 9. Mass spectrum of squalene (Exhibit 9).

Fig. 10. Mass spectrum of friedelan-3-one (Exhibit 2).

Fig. 11. Mass spectrum of 14B-pregnane (Exhibit 7)

Fig. 12. Mass spectrum of hop-22(29)-en-3-beta-ol (Exhibit 7).

Fig. 13. Mass spectrum of cholest-4-en-3-one (Exhibit 6).

Fig. 14. Mass spectrum of 1-octadecanol (stencil) (Exhibit 11).

ground substrate or in presence of variety of pyrolysates. Naturally, use of sensitive techniques is desirable for such investigations^{10,11}.

A reverse phase HPLC method was used by Dhole and Ghosal¹² for the detection and characterization of fire accelerants viz. petrol, gasoline, kerosene, diesel fuels and their residues (in arson cases). Lu and Harrington¹³ used gas chromatography-differential mobility spectrometry (GC-DMS) as a tool for analysis of ignitable residues from fire debris. Head space solid phase micro extraction (SPME) was applied as the pre concentration and sampling method.

Almirall *et al.*¹⁴⁻¹⁶, made extensive uses of solid phase micro extraction/gas chromatography in forensic analysis particularly for samples from fire debris. This may be followed by GC/MS analysis. However, there were cases of interfering ions from combustion and pyrolysis of substrate materials.

Almirall and Perr¹⁶ suggested the use of compound specific MS/MS for the identification of ignitable liquid residues in fire debris analysis. An ion was selected from MS experiment which might be the molecular ion or one of the fragment ions of the target analyte. Tandem mass spectrometry involved a second MS experiment on the isolated ion from the first experiment which was converted into fragments. The data conclusively proved the presence of the target analyte which was previously standardized in the same way.

Aziz *et al.*¹⁷ utilized pressure sensitive adhesive tapes representing key evidences of crimes such as assault, rape or homicide. The contents of the adhesive tapes were extracted by suitable solvent and GC-MS analysis was made to identify the hydrocarbons of importance. This method can be taken to be an appropriate method for on spot collection of evidences.

However, in the present investigation, gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer was utilized to confirm the pres-

ence of fuels and analyze the fuels present in the exhibits and in control samples. In bride burning cases, perpetrators use fuel as fire accelerants and invariably use petroleum products like kerosene, diesel, fuel oil, turpentine, petrol etc. These are highly inflammable fuels (ignition temperatures higher than 400 °C) but the temperature of fire from match sticks is sufficient to overcome the energy barrier to start combustion of fuels⁶. Generally, the rates of combustion, reactions are sufficiently high to burn the fire accelerators in a short time and the residues or fire debris may not give indication of burning due to fuels or kerosene (invariably used in Indian scenario) if they are not properly preserved, extracted and analyzed within a short time. Purified extracts from processing of the sent exhibits are usually low.

The results of GC-MS from the triplicate set of reading of the exhibits received from different regions showed that there were variations in chemical compositions in the constituents in kerosene but the most important aspect of the investigation is the presence of biomarkers in all the exhibits, a proof for the use of fuels. Biomarkers were variable. However, Friedelane-3-one was the common biomarker in exhibits 1, 2, 3, 4 (Delhi and neighborhood areas) and squalene was common in exhibits 5, 6, 9, 11, 12 (Delhi area), though there were other biomarkers like 14-B pregnane (Exhibits 7 and 8) together with HOP - 22 (29) - EN - 3 BETA. OL (Southern West Bengal area). Cadalene was obtained from Northern West Bengal area (Exhibit 10).

Systematic analysis of the bride burning data is difficult as fortunately bride burning cases are not of frequent occurrence. Many cases go unnoticed or are not properly investigated. Thus, only a limited number of samples were available. Moreover, crime cannot be repeated to get more samples. However, any homicidal burning case using fuel or fire accelerants can be analysed in the way described in this communication. Biomarkers are a group of com-

pounds, mainly hydrocarbons found in oils, rock extracts, soil extracts and sediment extracts. Biomarkers, known as “molecular fossils” are diagenetic alteration products of their biogenic precursors (terpenoids, sterols, steroids) in living organisms. Biomarker can be used to make oil-source rock correlations.

Biomarkers in an oil can reveal¹⁸⁻²¹

- (i) The relative amount of oil prone vs gas prone organic matter in the source kerogen.
- (ii) The age of source rock.
- (iii) The environment of deposition as marine, lacustrine, fluvio-deltaic or hypersaline.
- (iv) The source rock lithology (carbonate or shale).
- (v) The thermal maturity of the source rock during generation¹⁸⁻²¹.

However, biomarkers²¹ along with other hydrocarbons can be regarded to be positive and surest indicator of the presence of fire accelerators. Biomarkers, present in ppm and sub ppm level, are degradation resistant in the environment i.e. they withstand chemical, biochemical and thermal degradation. Forensic fingerprinting of biomarkers for oil spill characterization and source identification are now widely used in environmental forensic investigations^{22,23}. Biomarkers can be used to assess the origin of some refined hydrocarbon products^{20,21}. The biomarkers present in fire accelerators (kerosene) used were found to be distinctly different due to different sources or origin of petroleum crude for refining in different petroleum refineries in India like Digboi (Assam), Haldia (West Bengal), Barauni (Bihar), Mathura (Uttar Pradesh) etc. The identification of biomarkers should be potentially useful for forensic fire investigation. More work on biomarkers, the country of origin of crude oils and refineries involved in the processing of crudes are necessary to have better insight on fire accelerators. However, the investigators should collect not only garments etc., but try to collect samples of fire accelerators from the crime scene, for the experimental verification of the fire accelerators used. Crudes from different geographic sources are processed in different refineries. Thus, the fire accelerators like kerosene, petrol, diesels etc. obtained from different sources may be different in spite of the presence of large number of common biomarkers. But it will be inappropriate to tag the biomarkers to a definite source

or refinery and country of origin of petroleum crude without detailed biogeochemical studies. The culprits in bride burning cases are usually husband and/or in laws of bride but they cannot be apprehended without any positive proof. The identifications of biomarkers however, give positive evidences and better indications of the presence of fire accelerators in arson cases than Tandem Mass/Mass results which confirm the structure of a definite compound in question.

It is to be noted that every crime is individual and has its own history depending on places, time, socio-economic and other unknown conditions. Bride burning, prevalent in third world countries must not be appropriate for advanced countries like USA, UK etc. There may be other ways to deal similar cases like use of firearms, drugs with alcoholic beverages etc. In bride or other burning cases, the first hand information (or information from the local inhabitants) and other circumstantial evidences collected by the fire investigators or police officials from the scene of arson, the dying statement or statement during recovery of the victim supplemented by forensic investigations should be properly correlated to apprehend the culprits.

Conclusions :

The heinous crime like homicidal bride burning is widely prevalent in India and other South Asian countries. However, conclusive physical and chemical evidences with valid proof for bride burning (with probable culprits) are rarely available. Circumstantial evidences are poor. In bride burning cases, fire accelerators are invariably used. But the probability of the recovery of fire accelerators from the burnt fire debris or burnt wearing garments, bed sheets etc. are poor and uncertain. Chances of obtaining the presence of volatile fire accelerators obtained from burnt residues using gas chromatograph-headspace analysis are usually low as the low boiling hydrocarbons are lost. But gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer analysis of the analysates in diethyl ether can give enough evidence for the presence of fuels. But the surest proof for the use of accelerators is the identification of biomarkers in the fire residues. Biomarkers vary from place to place depending on the origin of fuel or petroleum products.

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